

CORRELATIONS BETWEEN WORK PERFORMANCE WITH EMPOWERING WORK CULTURE IN KABUPATEN NUNUKAN, KALIMANTAN UTARA, INDONESIA

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Abstract: The success of an organization depends on human resources as the main component that drives and gives direction to the organization. The achievement of a goal is usually influenced by various factors that are directly or indirectly related to the operating framework of the organization, especially work culture. Therefore, this study was conducted to identify the factors that still influence the work performance of staff in Kabupaten Nunukan based on the empowerment of work culture. Using quantitative methods (questionnaires), a total of 300 respondents were involved consisting of the Aparatur Sipil Negara (ASN). Correlation analysis shows that commitment, work discipline and work motivation are correlated with work performance. Therefore, it is hoped that this study can describe the real situation of ASN in improving job performance. ASNs are an important stage in governance as they act as intermediaries on behalf of superiors and subordinates. Strategic policies can be formulated so that the service delivery system by the government of Kabupaten Nunukan is at an optimal level in line with the vision of the Republic of Indonesia which is "*terwujudnya Indonesia maju yang berdaulat, mandiri, dan berkepribadian berdasarkan gotong royong*".

Keywords: work performance, work culture, empowerment, motivation, discipline, commitment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization or company depends on human resources as the main element or component that drives and gives direction to the organization or company (Dwi Mardiyanti, Nurdiana & Elin, 2019; Ginawati, Purwanti & Kasman). Human resources, especially those that are elements of leadership in formulating short-term and long-term strategies of the company, where the results obtained are for the welfare of employees or workers (Sidanti, 2015). However, the success is influenced by various factors, especially job performance factors (Sugiyono, 2018; Sunyoto, 2012). On the other hand, work performance that is done continuously and consistently will become a work culture that will ultimately drive the work performance of the workers themselves (Siagian, 2015; 2009).

In essence, work is a form or way for humans to actualize themselves (Suyadi & Dewi, 2015). Work is a real form of values, beliefs and can be a motivation to produce quality employees in achieving the vision or mission of an organization. Thoha (2015) divides work into eight doctrines namely work as grace, work is trust, work is a calling work is actualization, work is worship, work is art, work is honor and work is service. While Wright and Noe (2016) replaced the term work with the

word "employment". From these values, then there is a work culture (Zakaria, 2014: 1). Work culture is a philosophy based on the view of life as values that become the nature, habits and strengths, practices in the life of a group of people or organizations that are reflected from attitudes into behavior, beliefs, ideals, opinions and actions that materialize as "work or work" (Salasiah, Ermy Azziaty, Rosmawati & Zainab, 2012; Wang, Tsui & Xin, 2011).

So the success of development in an area is determined by the work performance of governments, both at the level of leaders (superiors) and at the level of workers (subordinates). Positive human resources (examples such as development outcomes) are considered a success by leadership (Pryce-Jones, 2011; Judge & Piccole, 2004). In addition, the success of development is also influenced by other factors that will ultimately form a positive work culture that is able to drive the work performance of each employee. Today's work culture is a big issue for governments as well as growing companies. Human resources (HR) are constantly changing in line with the development of the digital era at present (Rohani, Mustapah & Muhamad Ali, 2001; Neck & Milliman, 1994).

In Kabupaten Nunukan, work culture nowadays still unappropriated as expected, this can be seen from the results of the assessment in 2016-2018, where the values obtained are C and CC. The value is still not optimal. This is influenced by several indicators, including regulations that are constantly changing, the level of discipline of state civil servants / government employees that is always declining due to lack of work motivation and communication limitations between district and provincial government employees that still fail to be understood by the public.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Work performance is seen as a set of behaviors relevant to the achievement of organizational goals or the organizational unit in which a person works (Murphy, 1990 in Rambli 2001). Neol (2009) defines job performance as a process in which managers are responsible for ensuring that employee activities and productivity are in line with organizational goals. Work performance refers to behaviors or attitudes that indicate a person is related to his or her job and habits refer to actions and behaviors under an individual's control that contribute to organizational goals (Rotundo and Sackett, 2002). In the context of this study, job performance refers to the work results that have been achieved by a person in performing the tasks assigned to him.

In the public sector, the government has recommended a performance-based work culture by using key performance indicators or Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) applied in the public service to improve the quality of service delivery. In line with the vision, mission and functions of the agency, each organization needs to measure the performance of the services provided to ensure that all services are delivered to customers well. This can indirectly provide a clear picture of the performance of the organization as a whole.

In the study "The relationship between job satisfaction and job performance among workers in the manufacturing industry" by Rambli in 2001, several indicators as indicators of an employee's performance have been identified including the level of work attendance, punctuality, discipline during work, work quantity, quality of work and cooperative attitude. However, for public sector employees in particular, based on the Annual Performance Evaluation Report (LNPT) obtained from the Public Service Department (JPA), among the aspects taken into account to measure the performance of its employees are job production, knowledge and skills, personal qualities, intertwining relationships and collaborations as well as activities and contributions. In this study, job performance is seen based on two factors, namely commitment and motivation.

According to Mottaz (1988), commitment is the result of an affective response from an individual's evaluation of his or her work that may bind the individual to an institution or organization. According to Mottaz again, individuals join organizations to enable them to use skills, fulfill desires and achieve individual goals. If the organization is unable to provide opportunities for the individual, opportunities to achieve desires and goals, then individual commitment will vanish (Conger & Kanwgo, 2017; Boomert, 2016). In the context of this study, work commitment is seen as the effort, hard work and volunteerism of employees to contribute to organizational goals (Weber, 2016; George & Jones, 2016; Deschamps. Rinfret, Lagace & Privé, 2016).

A study conducted by Mazni (1996) found that the commitment of organizational members in the electronics factory in the state of Kedah has a significant relationship with the rewards they receive from the management of the factory. This means, members of the organization will work more diligently if the leaders in the organization care about their abilities and welfare.

The role of human resources in an organization is a very important determinant of the productivity and success of the organization in achieving its goals. A person's success in a field of work is determined by the level of competition, professionalism and also his commitment to the field he is involved in. As something that is positively related to a job, commitment is an attitude and behavior that can be seen as a motivator of a person in work is closely related.

In addition to organizational commitment, for the achievement of organizational goals in a better direction, motivation both internally and externally are very much emphasized and needed. Internal motivation is a motivation that arises from the mind, heart and self-desire. While external motivation is a motivation that arises due to the encouragement from outside the personal for example from others and from the organization of the workplace. According to Armstrong, motivation is something or a force that drives a person to perform certain actions or behaviors in certain ways (Badjuri, 2009).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study focuses on a quantitative method approach. To achieve the objectives of this study, the instrument for quantitative methods is through questionnaires. The population for this study is comprised of the Aparatur Sipil Negara (ASN). Based on the Sampling Table of Krejcie and Morgan (1970), the number of samples or respondents required is 246 respondents. This is because the number of ASNs in Kabupaten Nunukan in 2018 is 3,836 people. However, this study managed to get more respondents, namely 300 respondents. This shows that the response rate for this study is over 100.0 percent.

Correlation analysis shows the relationship between two variables. There are two types of correlation that exist between two variables, namely positive correlation and negative correlation. For this study, the correlation analysis is to see the relationship that exists between performance and the work culture of Kabupaten Nunukan's government staff. This analysis is also used to answer the third objective which is to identify the relationship between performance and the work culture of government staff in Kabupaten Nunukan.

The formula for obtaining the r-Pearson Correlation Coefficient is as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum(X-\bar{X})(Y-\bar{Y})}{(N-1)s_x s_y} \quad (3.1)$$

or

$$r_{xy} = \frac{\sum XY}{\sqrt{(\sum X^2)(\sum Y^2)}} \quad (3.2)$$

where:

r_{xy} = correlation coefficient between variable X and Y

N = sample size

X = the score value for the X variable

Y = the score value for the Y variable

s_x, s_y = standard deviation for X and Y

The correlation coefficient (r) is to show the degree of relationship between two variables. Briefly, r values are categorized as in Table I.

Table I: Correlation Coefficient Category (r)

<i>r Value</i>	Correlation
1.0	Perfect
0.80 – 0.90	Highly strong
0.60 – 0.79	Strong
0.40 – 0.59	Moderate
0.20 – 0.39	Weak
0.01 – 0.19	Highly weak
0.0	No correlation

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section is to discuss in more depth the factors that influence job performance based on work culture empowerment. Table 1 shows the findings of the regression analysis for apparatus commitment.

The results of the analysis show that the three dimensions of commitment, work discipline and work motivation statistically have a relationship with work performance at the 1% significance level (Table II.). The relationship that exists between work performance and the empowerment of work culture is at a moderate level, where the statistical value recorded is between 0.40 to 0.69 (commitment, 0.468; work discipline, 0.568; work motivation, 0.481). This finding simultaneously rejects the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between performance and the empowerment of government staff work culture in Kabupaten Nunukan.

Table II: Relationship Analysis of Work Performance with Work Culture Empowerment

Variables	Statistic
Commitment	0.468***
Dicipline	0.568***
Motivation	0.481***

Note: *** significant at 1%

5. RECOMMENDATION

For this study, improvement is the best step for the government in Nunukan Regency in improving work performance among staff. Based on the findings of the study, there are three main factors that need to be given attention by the government, namely:

- Commitment
- Discipline
- Motivation

In addition, in ensuring the improvement of staff performance in an administration, cooperation from both superiors and subordinates is important so that the service delivery process can be carried out effectively. Thus, a combination between Herzberg's Two -Factor Motivation Theory by Frederick Herzberg (1959) and Fiedler's Contingency Leadership Model (1967) is necessary in ensuring performance improvement over time.

The three main factors that have been mentioned namely apparatus commitment, work discipline and work motivation were found to be related to Herzberg's Two -Factor Motivation Theory by Frederick Herzberg (1959). With the presence of these three factors, this study is able to describe what qualities or criteria should be present in a leader in ensuring that their organization moves at an optimal level. Thus, Fiedler's (1967) Contingency Leadership Model is needed in guiding leaders in organizing their organizations without neglecting the needs of staff or employees. The relationship between the theory and the findings of the study is as shown in Figure 1. Figure 1 can also indirectly be used as a guide or recommendation for the empowerment of work culture and the impact on staff performance in Kabupaten Nunukan, North Kalimantan, Indonesia.

Figure 1: The Relationship between Theory and Factors Affecting Job Performance

Motivation is an indispensable element in any organization. Not only government or government organizations, but also from family institutions, education, business also need motivation. In this study, motivation is divided into two namely external motivation and internal motivation. External motivation is through the environment in which the staff works. Internal motivation is based on the motivation found in the staff. Internal motivation can indirectly affect external motivation. In shaping motivation the Theory of Reasonable Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1988) have described how these two theories help humans shape behavior and in turn create motivation in themselves and influence others.

With a positive motivation in yourself, this also affects the work discipline that is encouraging. For example, if an individual has good behaviors such as being punctual, he can naturally motivate himself to ensure that he attends the office on time and is able to complete assignments within a given period of time.

Positive motivation and behavior are not only seen to affect staff work discipline, but also affect commitment among the apparatus. As a middle officer, a high level of commitment needs to be shown to superiors and subordinates. With the presence of internal and external motivation, apparatus staff can formulate what the needs of superiors and subordinates in order to work together in achieving the mission and vision of the organization that has been set.

This shows that this study can apply Herzberg's Two -Factor Motivation Theory, namely through the determination of external motivation and internal motivation in identifying staff motivation among the apparatus. In Herzberg's Theory of Two Factor Motivation the terms motivation and hygiene are used. Where motivation represents intrinsic or internal factors and hygiene represents extrinsic or external factors.

Figure 1 also shows that with the work motivation, work discipline and commitment of the apparatus, indirectly it can form the nature of leadership among the apparatus. In this study, it is suggested that three aspects need to be emphasized in producing the best leadership among the apparatus in Kabupaten Nunukan, North Kalimantan, Indonesia, namely based on Fiedler's Contingency Leadership Model (1967).

In ensuring that the best leadership style is acceptable to staff, a leader needs to diversify his leadership style as proposed in Fiedler's (1967) Contingency Model. Where this model believes in leadership effectiveness varies depending on the situation. Although there are various forms of leadership applied, diversity of leadership is the best form of leadership to ensure the success and excellence of a governing body. Therefore, the study suggests that governments should develop these various forms of leadership by providing exposure to each form of leadership to old and new leaders through courses or programs to improve the knowledge and professionalism of leaders.

Leaders need to have a clear understanding of the dimensions of leadership such as charismatic dimensions, inspiring motivation, individual consideration and intellectual stimulation. Leaders also need to do their own research on the diversity of leadership implemented by looking at the studies that have been done as well as studies from outside or within the country.

The study suggests that governments identify leaders with a high level of leadership so that they can be placed in departments that are problematic from achievement. This is because according to Stoner and Wankel's (2015) study, leadership has great potential to mobilize declining organizations and help individuals find meaning and joy while working as well as in their lives.

The appointment of leaders as practiced now needs to be reviewed. In line with the changing times and circumstances, then the way of appointing leaders also needs to be modified and updated. Researchers suggest that a person to be appointed as a leader should be an experienced person, have high self-confidence and have been exposed to professionalism courses. Selection methods can also be varied for example selection through interviews and written tests. Therefore, it is hoped that through this method, a person who will be appointed as a leader is truly qualified and able to administer and lead an organization or governing body.

Leaders who have practiced certain leadership are encouraged to further strengthen that form of leadership. A precise and solid understanding of the dimensions of leadership can help the implementation of leadership effectively. Leaders need to model charismatic behavior, actions and thoughts to be an example and model to employees to succeed in the mission and vision of the organization that has been set. Leaders also need to have high abilities and skills in creating motivated employees so that all duties and responsibilities can be performed well and responsibly for the benefit and good of the organization.

In leadership, leaders also need to set aside any ego by considering each person as an individual and need to consider each employee as a very valuable human resource for the development of a country. Finally, leaders need to take advantage of existing opportunities especially through development slots. The professionalism of a leader to develop interest and stimulate the intellect of employees to be able to think more critically and creatively.

Diverse leadership styles in different situations are required. Positive rewards such as praise, recognition need to be provided to sustain performance. In addition, criticism and correction are also needed to correct mistakes in the process of leader preparation as well as career development. Practices like these usually keep performance in line with what is expected. This scenario explains the management perspective that emphasizes the need for subordinates to demonstrate the behaviors required for the achievement of organizational goals.

The success of a subordinate's career needs to be viewed holistically by looking at the characteristics of leadership. Colquit, LePine and Noe (2000) through a study, see personality as a balanced character that influences an action. This statement is also supported by Viswesvaran and Dilchert (2015) who describe personality as the disposition and consistent tendency of an individual in an action. Every leader must also emphasize the principle of rationality in making a decision and be responsible in every action taken. In ensuring the succession plan can be fully implemented, leaders must also have a personality explained through the study of Achua and Lussier (2013) that is a personality adapted to the work environment by adopting the Five Factor Model of Personality that is dimension, openness to change, prudence, consent and neuroticism.

Therefore, leaders with strong leadership patterns are needed to ensure that the ecology or environment of the organization can provide satisfaction to subordinates in determining their future direction. Thus ideal leadership is the result of comprehensive employee planning that requires an awareness of the leader's thinking in the work culture of the organization.

The effectiveness of a planned program is also influenced and shaped by the organizational environment. Bolman and Deal (2007) state that organizational weakness is also due to "focus too much on the actors and too little on the stage they play their role". Succession plan planning would be meaningless if the organizational climate and top management hindered initiative and stifled creativity. While subordinates are able to make career reforms, it depends on the transparency of top leaders to give recognition

6. SUMMARY

Administration or government collectively can be seen as a process that involves commitment between leaders and subordinates towards achieving the mission and vision of the organization. Accordingly, in today's world of public service environment, it demands a change in the way staffing is more effective and staffing the emotions of employees effectively in order to achieve the optimal level of competence.

In line with the principle of the public sector as the main organization contributing to national development, emphasis on personality traits, prudence as well as the ability to staff employees is seen as a very important instrument in improving staff performance in an organization or administration.

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